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Development of Cloud-Based e-Learning Repository using SHA-256 Cryptographic Hashing Algorithm

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Abstract

The advancement of information and communication technologies has transformed education through e-learning platforms, a shift accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic. At Babcock University, the absence of a centralized repository hampers efficient access to learning materials. To address this, a Cloud-based eLearning repository was developed using the SHA-256 cryptographic hashing algorithm for enhanced security. The system, designed with Unified Modeling Language and Agile methodology, employed HTML, CSS, and JavaScript for the front-end, PHP for the back-end, MySQL for authentication data, and Firebase for storing academic resources. Database stress tests exhibited stability and delivered satisfactory performance despite heavy data insertion, with execution times of 749 seconds for sequential reads, 308 seconds for sequential writes, 947 seconds for random reads, and 209 seconds for random writes. SHA-256 delivered strong results, averaging 11.8 cycles per byte and 1653 megabytes per second in throughput, which significantly enhances the security and reliability of the Cloud-based eLearning repository. The developed system demonstrated effectiveness in facilitating the process of making available course materials to students within the Babcock University community. Feedback from users highlights a generally positive experience with the system, emphasizing its ease of use and convenience.

Keywords: Cloud-based storage; eLearning; Firebase; Learning Management System; SHA-256 Cryptographic Hashing Algorithm; Throughput

1. Introduction

The rapid advancement of information and communication technologies (ICTs) has revolutionized the educational sector, giving rise to e-learning platforms that provide flexible, scalable, and widespread access to knowledge sources. The growing preference for online and blended learning models, further intensified by global disruptions like the COVID-19 pandemic, has increased the need for secure, reliable, and learner-centered e-learning infrastructures [1]. At the heart of these infrastructures lies the e-learning repository, a digital framework that collects, organizes, and distributes educational content, including lecture notes, multimedia, quizzes, and assignments [2]. To address the shortcomings of conventional repositories, including limited storage capacity, high maintenance expenses, and inadequate accessibility, cloud computing has emerged as an attractive solution by providing scalability, cost-effectiveness, and universal access [3,4]. Research has shown that students who utilize e-learning platforms benefit from better knowledge retention and enhanced flexibility in managing their academic, personal, and professional responsibilities [5]. The COVID-19 pandemic especially underscored the necessity for resilient e-learning systems in Nigerian universities to maintain educational continuity during disruptions [6].

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Nonetheless, as dependence on cloud-based repositories increases, so do concerns regarding data security, integrity, and trustworthiness. The open and distributed features of cloud environments expose them to threats such as unauthorized access, data manipulation, and identity impersonation, which jeopardize the confidentiality and authenticity of educational materials [6,7]. Maintaining data integrity and authenticity in e-learning repositories is especially vital, as compromised content can mislead learners, disrupt assessments, and diminish confidence in digital education systems. A promising strategy to tackle these issues is the implementation of cryptographic hashing algorithms. The Secure Hash Algorithm 256 (SHA-256) is widely acknowledged for its strength and resistance to collision and pre-image attacks [9]. SHA-256 converts input data into a distinct 256-bit fixed-length hash value, ensuring that even slight alterations to the initial data yield significantly different outputs [10]. This characteristic renders SHA-256 an effective method for verifying data integrity, identifying tampering, and authenticating users in cloud-based repositories [9,10].

Babcock University in Nigeria has increased its student enrolments from around 1,000 to over 20,000, highlighting the necessity for adopting digital transformation strategies to improve educational delivery [11]. Despite its progress, Babcock University faces numerous obstacles in meeting the requirements of contemporary digital learning. At present, the university does not have a centralized digital repository for educational resources, leading to difficulties in efficiently storing, managing, and sharing materials. Students frequently struggle to access vital course resources, which ultimately impact their academic performance and overall satisfaction. Additionally, the current infrastructure is constrained by limited storage capacity, inadequate resource management, and scalability challenges that hinder the institution's capability to support its increasing number of students. The implementation of a cloud-based e-learning storage repository at Babcock University would enable students to access important educational materials, such as lecture notes, previous examination papers, and multimedia files. This study aims to tackle these issues by creating a cloud-based e-learning repository that incorporates SHA-256 hashing. The goals include designing a cloud-hosted repository that is both scalable and accessible, integrating SHA-256 hashing to ensure the authenticity and integrity of educational materials, improving trust and security by reducing the risks of data tampering and unauthorized alterations, and assessing the performance, security, and usability of the proposed system in comparison to traditional repositories.

2. Review of Literature

The combination of cloud computing and digital technologies in higher education has garnered considerable academic interest, especially concerning e-learning, distance education, and digital transformation. Alam [12] proposed a conceptual framework for an adaptive e-learning ecosystem using cloud computing infrastructure. The study explored how cloud-based e-learning facilitates scalability, accessibility, and personalization in digital education. The study offered recommendations for optimizing cloud-based e-learning environments to enhance adaptability and user engagement but acknowledged the need for empirical validation of the suggested model to evaluate its effectiveness in practical settings. Hui *et al.* [13] conducted a research work that examined the role of cloud storage in academic settings, focusing on data security, accessibility, and usability among university students in Hong Kong. The study concluded with suggestions to bolster cloud storage security and user education in higher education; its findings were constrained to a specific demographic and therefore necessitate broader studies for generalizability. Talysheva *et al.* [14] looked into the uptake of electronic educational resources (EERs) and innovative technologies in university instruction. Relying on surveys conducted at various universities, the authors discovered that EERs boost student engagement and learning flexibility, but noted drawbacks such as insufficient technical infrastructure and resistance from faculty members who are untrained in digital tools.

Mpofu *et al.* [15] investigated how digital tools contribute to the advancement of teaching and learning within the context of higher education's digital transformation. Their research assessed how online educational technologies improve instructional delivery, student engagement, and access to knowledge. The authors recognized challenges such as limitations in infrastructure, gaps in digital literacy, and concerns regarding data security. The study concluded with strategic suggestions for optimizing the integration of technology for effective online learning, though it primarily relied on theoretical discourse without empirical validation of the suggested framework. Siddiqui *et al.* [16] focused on the use of cloud computing in e-learning, outlining both its benefits and challenges. The authors proposed strategies to enhance cloud-based e-learning platforms for improved outcomes but did not conduct an empirical evaluation of the tools discussed. Snoussi [17] carried out a review of some Learning Management Systems (LMS) within educational settings, concentrating on the opportunities and challenges they present. The research examined how LMS platforms aid in course management, resource distribution, and communication between students and educators. The study concluded with suggestions aimed at improving LMS effectiveness but lacked detailed strategies for implementation. Thavi *et al.* [18] evaluated the impact of cloud computing technologies on the education sector, highlighting both benefits and challenges. Their research showed that cloud solutions enhance accessibility, scalability, and cost efficiency

while promoting collaboration, resource sharing, and opportunities for remote learning. The study concluded with recommendations for optimizing the adoption of cloud computing in education but stressed the need for further refinement prior to practical implementation.

Vakaliuk *et al.* [19] examined the application of cloud technologies in distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic. The research emphasized benefits like accessibility, flexibility, and collaborative opportunities for students and educators alike. It also brought attention to challenges such as digital literacy gaps, technical issues, and cybersecurity threats. The authors recommended bolstering infrastructure, providing teacher training, and enhancing data security to make the most of cloud technologies in distance education. Velychko *et al.* [20] investigated the development of open educational resources (OERs) using cloud technologies within educational practices. The study, while recognizing the advantages of cloud platforms in resource creation, storage, and distribution, highlighted technical and pedagogical hurdles. The authors called for improved support and training to fully leverage the benefits of cloud-enabled OERs. Wu and Plakhtii [4] presented a theoretical overview of cloud computing in e-learning, concentrating on its architectural layers and deployment models. Involving 100 participants who tested the system, the findings indicated that the integration of cloud technologies enhanced training content and significantly improved academic performance. However, the study was constrained by a lack of thorough evaluation regarding system functionalities and security measures. The security of cloud-based e-learning repositories has emerged as a significant issue as educational institutions increasingly depend on digital platforms for storing knowledge, sharing resources, and facilitating collaborative learning [21]. Cryptographic methods, especially hashing algorithms like SHA-256 (Secure Hash Algorithm 256-bit), are often emphasized as essential tools for ensuring data integrity, authenticity, and secure access in these repositories [22]. SHA-256 is well-known for its strength against collision and preimage attacks, making it a fitting choice for protecting sensitive educational information stored in cloud environments [23]. In cloud-based e-learning systems, repositories frequently house a large volume of student records, instructional content, and assessment data that necessitate robust protection against tampering and unauthorized access [4,24]. By producing distinct hash values for digital assets, SHA-256 guarantees that any unauthorized changes to files can be identified, thus bolstering data integrity.

Numerous studies have explored the application of SHA-256 hashing for user authentication and access management in educational platforms [25]. For example, AlQahtani *et al.* [26] indicate that SHA-256 can be incorporated with password encryption and digital signatures to establish secure login systems in cloud-based learning management systems (LMS). This integration reduces the likelihood of credential theft and fosters trust between students and instructors. In a similar vein, Bandarapu *et al.* [27] assert that hash-based authentication methods utilizing SHA-256 are computationally efficient and well-adapted for large e-learning repositories that experience high traffic [28]. Cloud-based e-learning repositories face cyber threats, including unauthorized alterations to files and resource injections [25]. Several studies have highlighted that the implementation of SHA-256 hashing enables institutions to sustain the verifiable integrity of course materials and evaluations. In this regard, hashes function as digital fingerprints for files, allowing repositories to autonomously confirm whether learning resources have been altered (Gour *et al.*, 2025). This capability is especially critical for maintaining the authenticity of learning materials disseminated through open educational resources (OERs).

Despite the considerable research on cloud computing and digital technologies in higher education, several gaps still exist. A significant portion of the literature is either conceptual or theoretical, lacking extensive empirical validation of proposed models, which complicates the evaluation of their effectiveness in practical settings. Studies frequently concentrate on limited contexts, such as specific universities or the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic, which constrains the generalizability of the findings. Although challenges like data security, privacy, and infrastructure are regularly acknowledged, practical solutions, policies, and tested security measures remain insufficiently addressed. Specifically, SHA-256 hashing is recognized as an essential tool for securing cloud-based e-learning repositories by ensuring data integrity, authenticity, and effective authentication. Its resistance to collisions and computational efficiency render it appropriate for safeguarding academic information. The gap in the literature necessitated the development of a Cloud-based e-learning repository that incorporates SHA-256 hashing for Babcock University.

3. Methodology of the Proposed System

The study commenced with an extensive review of a wide range of literature, including published articles, peer-reviewed research papers, expert interviews, and relevant case studies, which were leveraged to derive insights into the problem domain. An in-depth analysis was conducted on existing e-learning platforms, storage systems, the current manual methods of academic and course material dissemination, and widely used cryptographic hash algorithms. This review aimed to assess their strengths, limitations, and overall relevance to the specific needs of the university. Based on the findings from this analysis, a conceptual design of a proposed system was developed to address the identified

shortcomings. The interview and discussion data collection methods were employed, which were conducted with lecturers, course coordinators, and students to gain a deeper understanding of the current academic resource-sharing processes. The system architecture was modelled using Unified Modeling Language (UML) to provide a clear and comprehensive blueprint, facilitating visualization of system components, interactions, and data flow. The Agile software development methodology was adopted for the implementation process due to its iterative nature, adaptability, and emphasis on continuous feedback, which ensures progressive refinement of the system. For the front-end development, HTML (HyperText Markup Language), CSS (Cascading Style Sheets), and Vanilla JavaScript were employed to create a responsive, intuitive, and user-friendly interface. PHP (Hypertext Preprocessor) was utilized for server-side operations and back-end logic, while MySQL (My Structured Query Language) served as the relational database management system to store user registration and login information. Firebase was integrated as the cloud storage solution for academic resources, providing scalable, real-time storage with high reliability. The system underwent rigorous database stress testing under varying load conditions to assess its performance, stability, and scalability. User evaluation was conducted through an online questionnaire, which was designed to measure key system attributes such as functionality, performance, compatibility, and usability. A pilot study of the survey was performed prior to the full-scale survey to validate the reliability of the questionnaire, with Cronbach's Alpha (α) employed as the reliability metric. Additionally, the SHA-256 cryptographic hashing algorithm was evaluated in terms of cycles per byte and throughput to ensure secure and efficient handling of sensitive data.

4. Proposed System Overview

The proposed system is a cloud-based e-learning platform for Babcock University that centralizes academic resources, including lecture notes, past questions, and multimedia content, through an intuitive interface organized by course and level. It features a "Resources" section and an interactive blog to support collaborative learning, multiple learning styles, and transparency through lecturer uploads, while enhancing security and reducing reliance on physical storage. The implementation of the cloud-based e-learning storage system involved the integration of multiple technologies. The front end was developed using modern technologies, including JavaScript (Vanilla and React). PHP was used for backend development due to its efficiency in handling dynamic content, compatibility with various web servers, and strong community support, enabling rapid development and customization. MySQL, a robust relational database management system, was employed to manage user authentication, including sign-up and login credentials, and cryptographic hashing techniques were used to enhance security. Firebase, a cloud-based NoSQL database, was used to manage academic resources dynamically, leveraging its real-time database capabilities for instant updates and synchronization of educational materials. Cloud storage in Firebase facilitated efficient organization and retrieval of academic files, including PDFs, lecture notes, and multimedia content.

5. Requirement Analysis

The requirements analysis phase lays the groundwork for developing a robust and user-focused cloud-based e-learning storage system. The functional requirements outline the essential capabilities expected from both the students' and administrators' perspectives. In contrast, the non-functional requirements outline aspects that are integral to the system's performance, availability, data integrity and security.

5.1. Functional Requirements

The functional requirements for the Cloud-Based e-Learning Repository is shown in Table 1.0.

Table 1 Functional Requirements for the Cloud-based eLearning Repository

CBER-FRID	FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENT DESCRIPTION
CBER-FR1	The system must allow user registration for different roles, including students, instructors, and administrators.
CBER-FR2	The System must allow the hashing of Passwords and sensitive data using SHA-256 for secure storage.
CBER-FR3	The system must provide a secure login for users, where user credentials are hashed with SHA-256 before storage

CBER-FR4	The system must allow password reset and recovery, ensuring new passwords are hashed with SHA-256 before updating the repository.
CBER-FR5	The system must use Role-Based Access Control to assign privileges and grant permission per role, allowing students to access materials and quizzes, instructors to manage courses and content, and administrators to oversee users and system policies.
CBER-FR6	The system must allow lecturers or instructors to upload, update, and delete course materials, including documents, PDFs, videos, quizzes, and interactive resources.
CBER-FR7	The system must allow administrators to upload, update, and delete academic resources.
CBER-FR8	The System must store metadata for each content item, including title, description,
CBER-FR9	The system must generate a SHA-256 hash for each uploaded file and student submission. It must use this hashing mechanism to verify integrity and ensure that content is not tampered with during storage or retrieval.
CBER-FR10	The system must detect and notify users if an uploaded or retrieved file has been tampered with (e.g., hash mismatch).
CBER-FR11	The system must securely store all file hashes in the database, preventing unauthorized modifications.
CBER-FR12	The system must enable students to access personalized academic resources tailored to their department, semester, and courses, with the ability to search using keywords, tags, course titles, or instructor names.
CBER-FR13	The system must allow students to search, view, and download learning materials from the repository, with search and sorting features that enable quick access to resources by course, semester, or resource type.
CBER-FR14	The system should provide a version control mechanism for uploaded content, ensuring older versions are accessible while maintaining integrity verification.
CBER-FR15	The system could allow discussion forums, comment sections, and messaging between students and instructors.
CBER-FR16	The System should allow notifications and alerts for new content, assignment deadlines, and forum responses.
CBER-FR17	The system shall generate reports for administrators on system usage, such as popular resources and user engagement levels.
CBER-FR18	The System must ensure automatic storage of all resources in the cloud.
CBER-FR19	The system must encrypt communication between client and server (e.g., HTTPS with TLS), in addition to SHA-256 hashing for content validation.
CBER-FR20	The system must allow instructors to share repository links with students for easy access.
CBER-FR21	The system must allow instructors to assign tasks and quizzes stored in the repository.
CBER-FR22	The system must maintain logs of all file uploads, downloads, and updates, including user details and timestamps.

* CBER – Cloud-based eLearning Repository Identification Number

5.2. Non-Functional Requirements

The Non-functional requirements of the Cloud-based eLearning Repository are shown in Table 2,0.

Table 2 Non-Functional Requirements for the Cloud-based eLearning Repository

TYPES OF NFRs	CBES-NFR-ID	NON-FUNCTIONAL REQUIREMENT DESCRIPTIONS
Security	CBER-NFR1	The System must use SHA-256 for hashing sensitive data such as passwords, files, and logs.
	CBER-NFR2	The System must use Role-based access control to prevent unauthorized access.
	CBER-NFR3	The System should implement secure connections using HTTPS.
	CBER-NFR4	The System must ensure that all databases are protected against data loss, corruption, and unauthorized modification.
	CBER-NFR5	The System must log every hash verification attempt for auditing and anomaly detection.
	CBER-NFR6	The System must authenticate users using a login ID and password before they are given access into the system,
Performance	CBER-NFR7	The System should be able to handle at least 1000 concurrent users without significant performance degradation.
	CBER-NFR8	The System should ensure that content retrieval and search results are returned within 2-3 seconds.
	CBER-NFR9	The System must ensure that hash computation and verification does not increase file upload or download time by more than 10% compared to baseline performance.
	CBER-NFR10	The System should allow fast and responsive interactions, including quick resource uploads and downloads.
Scalability	CBER-NFR11	The System should ensure that Cloud-based architecture allows horizontal scaling to accommodate increasing users and content storage needs.
	CBER-NFR12	The System must ensure that storage, compute, and network resources are scaled dynamically.
Reliability	CBER-NFR13	The System should ensure 99.9% uptime, allowing students to access resources without disruption.
	CBER-NFR14	The System must recover from failures within 5 minutes using backup and restore processes.
	CBER-NFR15	The System must ensure file integrity and must remain intact during recovery, with SHA-256 hashes re-verified after restoration.
	CBER-NFR16	The System must ensure that no data loss occurs during failures beyond the last automated backup window.
	CBER-NFR17	The System should ensure fault tolerance mechanisms are in place to ensure automatic failover in case of server or storage failure.
	CBER-NFR18	The System must ensure that no data loss occurs during failures beyond the last automated backup window.
Data Integrity	CBER-NFR19	The System must ensure that all uploaded and retrieved content maintains integrity using SHA-256 hashing algorithm.
	CBER-NFR20	The System must ensure that verification mechanisms are in place to detect any unauthorized file modification
	CBER-NFR21	The system should incorporate an intuitive and responsive user-friendly interface that requires minimal training for students, lecturers/instructors and administrators to navigate.

Usability	CBER-NFR22	The system must be accessible on multiple devices such as desktops, tablets, and smartphones.
	CBER-NFR23	The System should ensure that search and sorting support filters such as course, semester, instructor, keywords, and tags.
	CBER-NFR24	The System should send notifications and clearly inform users when uploads, downloads, or integrity checks succeed or fail.
Compliance	CBER-NFR25	The system must ensure adherence to data protection regulations, local data and international privacy laws.
	CBER-NFR26	The System must comply with accessibility standards (e.g., Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG) for inclusive design and other necessary professional regulations.

*NFRs – Non-Functional Requirements

* CBER-NFR-ID – Cloud-based eLearning Repository Identification Number

6. System Design

The Use case diagram was used to model the system. The Actors in the System, their roles, Preconditions, main flow and postconditions are:

6.1. Actors and their Use Cases

- **Student:** Register (Student), Login (Student), Access Materials, Download Resources, Search Resources (by keyword, tag, course, instructor), Filter & Sort Results, Participate in Discussion Forums, Comment on Resources, Messaging with Instructors and Receive Notifications (new content, deadlines, forum replies)
- **Instructor:** Register (Instructor), Login (Instructor), Upload Course Materials (PDF, Video, Interactive), Store Metadata (title, description, tags, upload date), Verify File Integrity (SHA-256) before storage, Create and Manage Discussion Forums, Respond to Comments, Messaging with Students and Receive Notifications (student submissions, forum updates)
- **Administrator:** Registration & Login Approvals, Manage Users (students, instructors, admins), Enforce Role-Based Access Control (RBAC), Password & Data Hashing (SHA-256), Monitor System Usage (logs, activity), Control Repository Policies and Generate Reports (user activity, system integrity)
- **System:** Hash Passwords, data & file using SHA-256 hashing algorithm, Verify File Integrity (uploads, retrievals), automatically store files in cloud storage, maintain metadata for resources, provide search indexing, enable filter & sort mechanism and send notifications (to students and instructors)

6.2. Preconditions

- The instructor or student must be registered and authenticated in the system.
- The user must have the required role-based permissions (instructors can upload, students can only download/view).
- The cloud repository must be accessible.

6.3. Main Flow (Normal Scenario)

- The instructor login to the repository using credentials that are hashed with SHA-256 before verification.
- The instructor selects "Upload Material" and chooses a file (e.g., lecture notes PDF).
- The system generates a SHA-256 hash of the uploaded file.
- The system stores the file in the cloud storage along with its corresponding hash value in the database.

A confirmation message is shown: "File uploaded successfully. Integrity secured with SHA-256."

Later, a student logs in to the system.

- The student searches for the uploaded file and selects "Download."
- The system retrieves the file from cloud storage.
- Before providing it to the student, the system recomputes the SHA-256 hash and compares it with the stored hash.

- At step 9, if the hash values do not match, the system blocks the download.
- The system displays an alert: "Integrity verification failed. File may be corrupted or tampered with."
- The event is logged and reported to the administrator for investigation
- If the hashes match, the system delivers the file to the student.
- The student successfully accesses the learning material, assured that it has not been tampered with.

6.4. Postconditions

- The uploaded file is stored in the cloud with its verified SHA-256 hash.
- The student retrieves only authentic and untampered content.
- Any detected tampering attempt is logged and flagged for administrative review.

The use case diagram is shown in Figure 1.0.

Figure 1 Use Case diagram of Cloud-based eLearning Repository System

7. Implementation of the Proposed System

The cloud-based e-learning storage system was developed using PHP for backend development, MySQL for managing user authentication data, and Firebase for cloud-based storage of academic resources. PHP was chosen for its efficiency in handling dynamic content, seamless integration with MySQL, and extensive community support, enabling rapid backend development. MySQL provided secure and structured storage for user credentials, enhanced with password and file contents hashing, while Firebase enabled real-time updates, synchronization, and organized storage of educational materials such as PDFs, lecture notes, and multimedia content. The system underwent rigorous testing to ensure functionality, performance, usability, and compatibility through alpha and beta testing. Alpha testing involved usability and performance assessments with recruited testers performing tasks such as signing up and accessing course materials, while feedback was collected to fix issues. Beta testing expanded this evaluation to external users, ensuring the system's appearance and functionality were optimal in web browsers and incorporating feedback to further refine the platform.

System security was ensured through Firebase authentication for secure identity verification via email/password, OAuth, multi-factor authentication and SHA-256 hashing algorithm, along with Firebase security rules for dynamic access control. Course contents and passwords were hashed using the SHA-256 hashing algorithm and access was restricted based on user roles to prevent unauthorized interactions. Maintenance strategies included regular daily backups of all data and configurations, scheduled updates to address security vulnerabilities and improve performance, and proactive monitoring to ensure the system remains secure, reliable, and up-to-date. Some of the snapshots of the implementation are shown in Figure 2.0, 3.0, 4.0 and 5.0. This snapshot illustrates the main signup interface where users initiate the registration process for the system.

Figure 2 Signup Page

Figure 3 Sign Up as Student page

Figure 4 Course Level Page

Figure 5 Semester Course Page

8. Results and Discussion of Results

The system has effectively facilitated the dissemination of course materials within the Babcock University community. User feedback reflects predominantly positive experiences, highlighting the platform's intuitive interface, ease of use, and convenience. Performance assessments show satisfactory speed, reliability, and functionality. Evaluation details of the proposed system are provided in sections 8.1, 8.2, and 8.3.

8.1. Database Stress Testing

Experimental testing was conducted in a controlled virtual machine environment to rigorously evaluate the operational performance of the Cloud-Based e-Learning Repository platform. The testbed included ten(10) Intel Core i5 CPU physical machines, which simulated client-side requests, and five (5) virtual machines, which supported platform deployment and data management. Of the virtual machines, two functioned as application servers hosting the operating environment and platform modules. The remaining three virtual machines provided resource storage services. The stability and efficiency of the platform depend on the performance of its core databases, Firebase and MySQL. To assess their resilience under load, stress tests were conducted using four performance metrics: sequential read, sequential write, random read, and random write. Simulated data was inserted into the databases to emulate large-scale operational demands. The experimental results, presented in Table 3.0 and Figure 6.0, reveal that the total execution time for sequential read operations was 749 seconds, while sequential write operations required 308 seconds. In contrast, random read operations recorded a higher execution time of 947 seconds, whereas random write operations achieved the lowest execution time of 209 seconds. These results indicate that, even under conditions of large-scale data

insertion, both databases exhibited stable operational performance and sustained satisfactory outcomes in data rate stress evaluations.

Table 3 Database Stress Tests for the Cloud-Based e-Learning Repository

S/NO	Database Performance Metric	Total execution time (seconds)
1	Sequential Read	749
2	Sequential Write	308
3	Random Read	947
4	Random Write	209

Figure 6 Database Stress Tests for the Cloud-Based e-Learning Repository -

8.2. Evaluation of the SHA-256 Cryptographic Hashing Algorithm

SHA-256 significantly enhances the security and reliability of a cloud-based eLearning repository. It maintains data integrity by generating unique digital fingerprints for files, allowing the system to identify any unauthorized modifications to learning materials which is crucial for Open Educational Resources (OERs). SHA-256 also supports secure authentication mechanisms, reducing the risk of credential theft and promoting trust between students and instructors. Its computational efficiency enables effective management of large repositories with substantial content and user activity. Furthermore, the algorithm's strong resistance to collision and pre-image attacks ensures the authenticity and uniqueness of learning resources, facilitating the issuance of tamper-proof digital certificates. The SHA-256 cryptographic hashing algorithm was evaluated for cycle per byte and throughput. The results are shown in Table 4.0.

Table 4 SHA-256 Performance Evaluation

SHA-256 Performance Metrics	Values
Average Cycle per Byte	11.86cpb
Average Throughput	1653mps

8.3. Users' Behavioural Attributes Evaluation

User evaluation was conducted through an online questionnaire that uses a 5-point Likert scale to assess the functionality, performance, compatibility, and usability of the proposed system. The internal consistency of the questionnaire was examined using Cronbach's alpha, which quantifies the internal consistency on a standardized scale from 0 to 1. The analysis yielded a coefficient of $\alpha = 0.916$, which exceeds the commonly accepted threshold of 0.70, thereby demonstrating a high level of reliability which indicates that the questionnaire is highly dependable and that

the collected data can be confidently trusted. This result confirms that the measurement metrics are consistent and that the instrument can be considered a valid and trustworthy tool for data collection. The detailed evaluation results for functionality, performance, compatibility, and usability are presented in Table 5.0 and illustrated in Figure 7.0.

Table 5 Users’ Behavioural Attributes Evaluation

Users’ Behavioural Attributes Metrics	Value (%)
Functionality	98%
Performance	97%
Usability	96%
Compatibility	89%

Figure 7 Users’ Behavioural Attributes Evaluation

9. Conclusion and Future Works

This study presents the development of a Cloud-based eLearning Repository System aimed at enhancing academic resource management for students at Babcock University. The system provides a centralized repository for the storage and retrieval of lecture notes, past examination questions, multimedia course materials, and other academic resources. By consolidating diverse materials within a unified and accessible platform, the system advances the efficiency of academic resource management and improves the overall student learning experience. User feedback informed the inclusion of features such as blog and poll posting, controlled access to academic resources, and administrative and security mechanisms. Security was reinforced through the implementation of the SHA-256 cryptographic hashing algorithm, which ensures data integrity, supports secure authentication, and detects unauthorized alterations to files. Usability testing confirmed that the interface is intuitive and user-friendly, supporting easy navigation, effective communication, and broad accessibility, while user evaluations consistently emphasized the system’s convenience and its positive influence on resource accessibility and academic engagement. Performance validation through database stress testing demonstrated the system’s robustness, with consistent throughput under varying workloads and operating conditions. The deployment of SHA-256 hashing enhanced security within the repository by safeguarding learning resources, enabling tamper-proof digital certification, and mitigating collision and pre-image attacks. These measures collectively strengthened user trust while ensuring secure management of large volumes of educational content.

The implementation of this system represents a significant advancement in educational management technologies, underscoring the potential of cloud-based platforms to streamline administrative processes, increase student efficiency, and provide scalable models for institutional adoption. Future research should prioritize enhancing user experience through advanced search algorithms, mobile application integration, richer reporting mechanisms, and gamification features to promote learner engagement. In addition, exploring the interoperability with established learning management systems, alongside the development of robust security and privacy frameworks, is critical for safeguarding

sensitive academic data. The integration of artificial intelligence will further present opportunities to deliver personalized learning pathways tailored to individual student needs. Addressing infrastructural limitations, particularly through offline accessibility and optimization for low-bandwidth environments to ensure the long-term sustainability, reliability, and effectiveness of Cloud-based eLearning Repository Systems.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

References

- [1] H. Eljak, A. O. Ibrahim, F. Saeed, I. A. T. Hashem, A. Abdelmaboud, H. J. Syed, and A. Elsafi, "E-learning-based cloud computing environment: A systematic review, challenges, and opportunities," *IEEE Access*, vol. 12, pp. 7329–7355, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/10341232/>
- [2] A. Martinez-Garcia, P. Horrach-Rosselló, and C. Mulet-Forteza, "Evolution and current state of research into E-learning," *Heliyon*, vol. 9, no. 10, 2023. [Online]. Available: [https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440\(23\)08224-5](https://www.cell.com/heliyon/fulltext/S2405-8440(23)08224-5)
- [3] L. A. Hussein and M. F. Hilmi, "Cloud computing-based e-learning in Malaysian universities," *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (Online)*, vol. 15, no. 8, p. 4, 2020. [Online]. Available: <https://www.proquest.com/docview/2666937229?fromopenview=true&pq-origsite=gscholar>
- [4] W. Wu and A. Plakhtii, "E-learning based on cloud computing," *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)*, vol. 16, no. 10, pp. 4–17, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/220086/?nl=1>
- [5] T. Hongsuchon, I. M. E. Emary, T. Hariguna, and E. M. A. Qhal, "Assessing the impact of online-learning effectiveness and benefits in knowledge management, the antecedent of online-learning strategies and motivations: An empirical study," *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 5, p. 2570, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/14/5/2570>
- [6] A. M. Maatuk, E. K. Elberkawi, S. Aljawarneh, H. Rashaideh, and H. Alharbi, "The COVID-19 pandemic and E-learning: challenges and opportunities from the perspective of students and instructors," *Journal of Computing in Higher Education*, vol. 34, no. 1, pp. 21–38, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12528-021-09274-2>
- [7] G. Kaur and S. Singh, "A review on cloud security challenges and its future directions," *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research Academy*, vol. 8, no. 10, pp. 1–?, 2018. [Online]. Available: <http://www.ijmra.us>
- [8] T. Digambar, "Security issues with cloud computing," *Journal of Scientific Research and Technology*, pp. 1–6, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.jsrtjournal.com/index.php/JSRT/article/view/181>
- [9] L. N. Degambur, S. Armoogum, and S. Pudaruth, "A study of security impacts and cryptographic techniques in cloud-based e-learning technologies," *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 13, no. 1, 2022. [Online]. Available: https://researchgate.net/profile/Sameerchand_Pudaruth2/publication/358335417_A_Study_of_Security_Impacts_and_Cryptographic_Techniques_in_Cloud-based_e-Learning_Technologies/links/6200861db44cbe4227296a0f
- [10] B. U. I. Khan, R. F. Olanrewaju, M. A. Morshidi, R. N. Mir, M. L. B. M. Kiah, and A. M. Khan, "Evolution and analysis of secure hash algorithm (SHA) family," *Malaysian Journal of Computer Science*, vol. 35, no. 3, pp. 179–200, 2022. [Online]. Available: <http://jice.um.edu.my/index.php/MJCS/article/view/35355>
- [11] Babcock University, "Home page," 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.babcock.edu.ng/>
- [12] A. Alam, "Cloud-based e-learning: Development of conceptual model for adaptive e-learning ecosystem based on cloud computing infrastructure," in *Proc. Int. Conf. Artificial Intelligence and Data Science*, Cham, Switzerland: Springer Nature, Dec. 2021, pp. 377–391. [Online]. Available: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-21385-4_31

- [13] S. C. Hui, M. Y. Kwok, E. W. Kong, and D. K. Chiu, "Information security and technical issues of cloud storage services: A qualitative study on university students in Hong Kong," *Library Hi Tech*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 1406–1425, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.emerald.com/lht/article-abstract/42/5/1406/1233423/Information-security-and-technical-issues-of-cloud?redirectedFrom=fulltext>
- [14] I. Talysheva, K. Pegova, and L. Khaliullina, "The use of electronic educational resources of the university as a means of increasing the educational motivation of students," *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (iJET)*, vol. 16, no. 1, pp. 289–304, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/dc61/4e85032b05c0adac2352e646bb6e7d4c54e9.pdf>
- [15] A. C. Mpofu, F. Y. Mpofu, F. Mantula, and S. Ndlovu, "The essentials or fundamentals for harnessing technologies to improve teaching and learning through online learning as part of digital transformation in higher education," *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 2488–2502, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://econpapers.repec.org/article/bcpjournal/v_3a8_3ay_3a2024_3ai_3a1_3ap_3a2488-2502.htm
- [16] S. T. Siddiqui, S. Alam, Z. A. Khan, and A. Gupta, "Cloud-based e-learning: Using cloud computing platform for an effective e-learning," in *Smart Innovations in Communication and Computational Sciences: Proc. ICSICCS-2018*, Singapore: Springer Singapore, 2018, pp. 335–346. [Online]. Available: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-13-2414-7_31
- [17] T. Snoussi, "Learning management system in education: Opportunities and challenges," *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, vol. 8, no. 12S, pp. 664–667, 2019. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Thouraya-Snoussi/publication/337887753_
- [18] R. Thavi, R. Jhaveri, V. Narwane, B. Gardas, and N. Jafari Navimipour, "Role of cloud computing technology in the education sector," *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 182–213, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.emerald.com/jedt/article-abstract/22/1/182/1236226/Role-of-cloud-computing-technology-in-the?redirectedFrom=fulltext>
- [19] T. A. Vakaliuk, O. M. Spirin, N. M. Lobanchykova, L. A. Martseva, I. V. Novitska, and V. V. Kontsedailo, "Features of distance learning of cloud technologies for the organization educational process in quarantine," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 1840, no. 1, p. 012051, 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1840/1/012051/meta>
- [20] V. Y. Velychko, E. G. Fedorenko, V. N. Soloviev, and L. V. Dolins'ka, "Creation of open educational resources during educational practice by means of cloud technologies," *CTE Workshop Proceedings*, vol. 9, pp. 278–289, Mar. 2022. [Online]. Available: <http://ceur-ws.org/Vol-3098/paper20.pdf>
- [21] Q. Alajmi and G. J. Chellathurai, "Adoption of cloud computing in e-learning systems: Security perspective review," *Tasnim International Journal for Human, Social and Legal Sciences*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 356–374, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://tasnim-lb.org/index.php/ijhs/article/view/107>
- [22] Y. Xu, K. He, R. Wang, M. Yu, N. Duffield, H. Wassel, and A. Vahdat, "Hashing design in modern networks: Challenges and mitigation techniques," in *Proc. USENIX Annual Technical Conf. (USENIX ATC)*, 2022, pp. 805–818. [Online]. Available: <https://www.usenix.org/conference/atc22/presentation/xu>
- [23] A. Sevin and Ü. Çavuşoğlu, "Design and performance analysis of a SPECK-based lightweight hash function," *Electronics*, vol. 13, no. 23, p. 4767, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2079-9292/13/23/4767>
- [24] S. Rani, S. Rani, and V. Singh, "Security enhancement using cryptography in cloud-based education portals," in *Proc. 3rd Int. Conf. Artificial Intelligence: Advances and Applications (ICAAIA 2022)*, Singapore: Springer Nature, 2023, pp. 505–516. [Online]. Available: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-19-7041-2_42
- [25] M. M. Özcan, B. A. Ayaz, M. M. Karagöz, and E. Yolaçan, "Performance evaluation of SHA-256 and BLAKE2b in proof of work architecture," *Eskişehir Türk Dünyası Uygulama ve Araştırma Merkezi Bilişim Dergisi*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 60–65, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/pub/estudambilisim/issue/68981/1086400>
- [26] A. A. S. AlQahtani, Z. El-Awadi, and M. Min, "A survey on user authentication factors," in *Proc. IEEE 12th Annual Information Technology, Electronics and Mobile Communication Conf. (IEMCON)*, 2021, pp. 323–328. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/abstract/document/9623159/>
- [27] S. R. Bandarapu, M. Bilal, P. Chatterjee, A. M. Cheema, J. Rashid, and J. Kim, "Blockchain-based federated learning framework for malicious node detection in internet of vehicles (IoV) networks using fog and cloud computing," *Journal of King Saud University - Computer and Information Sciences*, vol. 37, no. 6, p. 120, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s44443-025-00134-y>

- [28] M. Pandya, "Performance evaluation of hashing algorithms on commodity hardware," arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.08284, 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2407.08284>
- [29] A. Gour, S. Singh, and M. Kapoor, "Ensuring security and privacy in cloud-based EHRs: A proposed framework for modern manufacturing and healthcare systems," in *Advanced Manufacturing Processes*, Boca Raton, FL, USA: CRC Press, 2025, pp. 112–137. [Online]. Available: <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/edit/10.1201/9781003476238-8/ensuring-security-privacy-cloud-based-ehrs-ayush-gour-suresh-singh-monit-kapoor>